

(II) ***Henckelia bifolia* (D. Don) A. Dietr. New Distributional Records for Maharashtra**

Khandesh region consist of three districts Jalgaon, Dhule and Nandurbar. It lies between 20°8' and 22° 7' North latitude and 73°42' and 76°28' East longitude. Khandesh covers a total area of 26,703.36 Km². The forest of Satpuda range is mostly of the dry mixed deciduous type and one of the important forests of Maharashtra in India. The flora shows much more diversity with the change in topography. The vegetation varies considerably with the change in altitude, soil, temperature, humidity and rainfall. Khandesh region though botanically rich in biodiversity have not been explored extensively except a few sporadic reports on floristic of Karnik, 1959; Salunkhe, 1995; Khan *et al.*, 2015; Khan and Firdousi, 2019.

During botanical exploration of Khandesh region in Maharashtra one interesting species *Henckelia bifolia* (D. Don) A. Dietr. (Gesneriaceae) was collected from moist shady hill slopes. The species was identified with the help of pertinent literature Clarke (1884) and Mudgal *et al.* (1997) and the taxa were confirmed by Dr. Milind Sardesai, Department of Botany, Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune. Dr. Rajeev Kumar Singh (BSI) Coimbatore and by consulting the Botanical Survey of India Western Circle, Pune, herbarium as well. The species is now reported for the first time from

Maharashtra. The voucher specimens have been deposited in the herbarium of Department of Botany, H.J. Thim College of Arts and Science Mehrun, Jalgaon, Maharashtra.

Henckelia bifolia (D. Don) A. Dietr., Sp. Pl., ed. 6, 1: 574. 1831; Sinha and Datta in Nelumbo 58: 24. 2016; Hillard in Grierson and Long, Fl. Bhutan 2(3): 1320. 2001. *Chirita bifolia* D. Don, Prodr. Fl. Nepal. 90. 1825; Clarke in Hook. *f.*, Fl. Brit. India 4: 357. 1884; Mudgal *et al.*, in Fl. M. P. 2: 257. 1997 (Fig. 1).

Herbs, erect, 7-15 cm high; rhizomes elongated or tuberous, hairy; stems with 1-2 small, bract like leaves in the middle. Leaves 2, unequal, orbicular; larger leaf 3-5 cm long; smaller leaf 1-3.5 cm long, sometimes suppressed, cordate at base, serrate, densely villous. Peduncles 1-2 between the leaves, 2-fid, 1-2.5 cm long; bracts 6-7 mm long, villous. Flowers solitary; pedicels 8-12 mm long, pubescent. Calyx 10-13 mm long, subcorollaceous; lobes lanceolate, 8-9 mm broad. Corolla purple-blue above, yellowish below, 3.5-5 cm long, ventricose above the calyx. Stamens 2 fertile, filaments hairy at the top. Ovary and style pubescent, stigma peltate, oblique, notched on the lower side. Capsules sessile linear.

Fig. 1: *Henckelia bifolia* (D. Don) A. Dietr.

Flowering and Fruiting: August-September

Distribution: Himalayas from Himachal Pradesh to Arunachal Pradesh, Nepal and Bhutan.

Specimens examined: Nandurbar Dist. Toranmal TAK 6482; Akkrani TAK 7492; Amlibari forest, TAK 8571. (N 21°40' 23.27" E 74°1'30.43", 684.2 m).

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